

Table 1 Hormone analysis of urine samples obtained from women with known male and female offspring sex outcomes.

Sample #	Sex	Testosterone ng/ml	Estradiol ng/ml	Estriol ng/ml	Estrone ng/ml	Progesterone ng/ml	hCG mIU/ml	Oxidizing minus reducing	Overall reaction	FRAP test	PTA test
1	M	4.4	1.0	42.2	0.3	11.3	0.0	27.7	Oxidizing	Yellow	White
2	M	6.1	3.5	167.7	4.5	109.0	20.4	40.3	Oxidizing	Yellow	White
3	M	14.4	1.3	388.0	1.0	78.3	0.0	297.6	Oxidizing	Yellow	White
4	M	21.9	20.9	1919.8	19.8	444.1	0.5	1494.0	Oxidizing	Yellow	White
5	M	11.6	28.8	310.5	34.7	176.2	6.2	180.1	Oxidizing	Yellow	White
6	M	22.9	32.1	426.8	15.5	333.8	0.0	117.7	Oxidizing	Yellow	White
7	F	19.6	20.4	444.7	16.0	518.9	0.0	-57.4	Reducing	Blue	Clear
8	F	6.8	4.4	97.4	1.0	218.4	6.3	-128.7	Reducing	Blue	Clear
9	F	8.0	8.5	330.6	1.7	227.0	250.0	-144.1	Reducing	Blue	Clear
10	F	68.0	10.4	104.5	10.0	151.5	3.2	-97.8	Reducing	Blue	Clear
11	F	33.6	14.9	348.6	11.8	1106.3	0.0	-764.7	Reducing	Blue	Clear

Please note that these samples were kept at room temperature for over 10 years without any preservative. These data show that hormones are robust molecules. While some derivatization may have been present, the redox properties remained inherently the same.